

Synthesis, physicochemical characteristics and biological activity of ruthenium(III) complexes with bidentate (N, O) Schiff bases

Bipin H. Mehta* and Sameer D. Disale

Department of Chemistry, University of Mumbai, Vidyanagari, Kalina, Santacruz (E), Mumbai-400 098, India

E-mail : bipin_281050@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 11 November 2010, revised 05 May 2011, accepted 20 June 2011

Abstract : The octahedral ruthenium(III) complexes have been prepared with bidentate Schiff bases derived from condensation of 2-amino-4-methylpyridine and 4-methylaniline with aromatic aldehydes. The obtained complexes were characterized on the basis of their elemental analysis, electronic spectra, magnetic moment, IR and ^1H NMR spectroscopy as well as thermal analysis. The ruthenium(III) complexes belong to low spin d^5 configuration. Spectral (IR, ^1H NMR) studies shows that all the Schiff bases behave as bidentate ligands and coordinated to ruthenium metal atom via nitrogen and oxygen. The Schiff bases and their complexes have been screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) activities by disc diffusion method.

Keywords : Schiff base, Ru^{III} complexes, antibacterial studies.

Introduction

Metal complexes of Schiff bases are of considerable interest and they have played a central role in the inorganic chemistry of chelate systems. Schiff bases and their metal complexes exhibit various biological activities, in particular, anticarcinogenic¹ and antitumor activities² because of their specific structures. The growing interest of the chemists in the study of the ruthenium complexes³⁻⁶ is due to their interesting electron-transfer properties and plays an important role in chemical and biological processes⁷. Change in coordination environment around ruthenium is an important in modulating the properties of the complexes. The presence of N and O donor atoms turns the properties of the complexes to a great extent as effective and stereo specific catalysts for oxidation, reduction and hydrolysis⁸⁻¹⁰. These types of complexes are also reported to have antiviral and antibacterial activity¹¹ and are known to serve as models for biologically important species which contain metal ion in macrocyclic environment. There is continued interest in ruthenium(III) Schiff base complexes owing to their importance in oxidation processes^{12,13}. Although there is a wealth of information on the transition metal complexes containing Schiff bases¹⁴, it is largely confined to the first row metals, notably iron, cobalt and nickel^{15,16}. Very little work has been reported on the Schiff base complexes of ruthenium^{17,18}. In view of the growing interest in the biological and catalytic ac-

tivities of ruthenium complexes, in this communication we report the synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity of ruthenium(III) complexes of bidentate Schiff bases.

Results and discussion

The complexes were prepared by reacting Schiff base ligands with metal ion in 2 : 1 mole ratio in an ethanolic medium. All Schiff bases behave as bidentate ligands and coordinate through nitrogen and oxygen atoms. Physical and analytical data of the Schiff bases and their ruthenium(III) complexes corresponds to the composition as shown in Table 1. The analytical data and spectral analysis agree well with the proposed composition of ruthenium(III) complexes of bidentate Schiff bases. The molar conductivity of the complexes in $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution in DMSO lies in the range of 4–16 $\text{S cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating their non-electrolytic behavior¹⁹. Thus, the complexes may be formulated as $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{XY}]$, (where, X = Cl^- and Y = H_2O). The data obtained allows us to ascribe the structure Fig. 1 of as synthesized $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ complex of bidentate Schiff base ligand.

The IR spectra of the free Schiff bases were compared with those of the ruthenium complexes to study the binding mode of the Schiff base ligands to ruthenium metal ion in the complexes, Table 2. A broad band appear at $3300\text{--}3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristics of hydrogen bonded $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the ligand and metal complexes

Comps.	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Mol. wt.	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	Cl	Ru
HL ¹	Orange	90	242.29	68.98 (69.40)	5.69 (5.82)	11.18 (11.56)	-	-
[C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂]								
HL ²	Orange	100	241.31	74.45 (74.66)	6.19 (6.27)	5.86 (5.80)	-	-
[C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N]								
HL ³	Yellow	118	241.31	74.74 (74.66)	6.23 (6.27)	5.79 (5.80)	-	-
[C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N]								
[Ru(L ¹) ₂ Cl.H ₂ O]	Green	> 300	637.16	52.90 (52.78)	4.36 (4.43)	9.02 (8.79)	5.38 (5.56)	15.64 (15.86)
[Ru(C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₄ Cl.H ₂ O)]								
[Ru(L ²) ₂ Cl.H ₂ O]	Black	> 300	635.16	55.59 (56.73)	4.38 (4.76)	4.21 (4.41)	5.49 (5.58)	16.15 (15.91)
[Ru(C ₃₀ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₂ Cl.H ₂ O)]								
[Ru(L ³) ₂ .Cl ₂]	Reddish-black	> 300	652.59	55.01 (55.22)	4.15 (4.33)	3.98 (4.29)	10.51 (10.87)	16.18 (15.49)
[Ru(C ₃₀ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂)]								

Fig. 1. Structure of [Ru(L¹)₂Cl.H₂O].

stretching vibration²⁰. Strong absorption bands at the 1597, 1618 and 1624 cm⁻¹ are observed in the free Schiff bases, which are characteristic of the azomethine (-HC=N) group. These bands shifted to the lower wavenumber in all ruthenium(III) complexes by 14–26 cm⁻¹, there should be a reduction in electron density in the azomethine link leading to lowering of the -HC=N frequency. This clearly indicates the coordination of the Schiff bases through the azomethine nitrogen²¹. Also strong evidence is the appearance of bands in the range 560–672 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{Ru-N}}$ ^{22,23}. Whereas the high-in-

Table 2. IR, UV-Visible spectral, molar conductivity and magnetic susceptibility data of Schiff base and metal complexes

Comps.	IR spectral data (cm ⁻¹)				Molar cond. (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Electronic spectral data			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ru-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ru-O}}$		λ (nm)			
						$(\epsilon \text{ in dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1})$			
HL ¹	1374	1597	-	-	4.2	313.5 (108025)	273.5 (72148)	253.5 (67034)	-
HL ²	1363	1618	-	-	3.6	322.0 (152205)	282.0 (111869)	251.5 (71130)	-
HL ³	1384	1624	-	-	3.9	332.5 (86285)	286.5 (49295)	250.5 (36912)	-
[Ru(L ¹) ₂ Cl.H ₂ O]	1320	1583	560	461	15.6	615.0 (14761)	260.0 (390437)	240.5 (233056)	1.79
[Ru(L ²) ₂ Cl.H ₂ O]	1316	1599	576	457	13.5	575.0 (103734)	262.0 (364315)	238.0 (201452)	1.93
[Ru(L ³) ₂ .Cl ₂]	1364	1598	623	479	12.7	519.5 (60166)	260.0 (224066)	244.5 (159751)	1.84

tensity band around 1363–1384 cm^{-1} in the Schiff bases is due to the phenolic C–O stretching. In complexes the phenolic oxygen of Schiff bases is coordinated with the metal ion by loss of proton, which is confirmed by C–O stretching vibration appear at a lower frequency value²⁴, 1316–1364 cm^{-1} . In addition, all complexes shows additional weak to medium intensity bands in the region 450–470 cm^{-1} which are absent in the IR spectra of ligands, these can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{Ru-O}}$ stretching^{22,23}. Thus IR spectra give evidence that bonding of ligand to metal ion through nitrogen and oxygen. Fig. 2 (A and B) shows the IR spectra of ligand HL¹ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

Fig. 2. (A) IR spectra of HL¹ and (B) $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

The electronic absorption spectral data of ligands and their ruthenium(III) complexes are shown in Table 2. The spectra of the ligands showed three high intensity bands at 31897, 36697 and 39525 cm^{-1} indicating $n \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions respectively. The electronic absorption spectral data of the complexes suggest octahedral nature of the complexes. The ground state of ruthenium(III) is $^2T_{2g}$, which are known to arising from the $t_{2g}^5 (t_{2g}^4 e_g^1)$ configuration in an octahedral environment. The excited states are $^2A_{2g}$, $^2T_{1g}$ and 2E_g which arise from $t_{2g}^4 e_g^1$ configuration²⁵⁻²⁸. In the hexa coordinated ruthenium(III) complexes, charge transfer transition often occurs at relatively low energy. The hole in the low spin t_{2g}^5 configuration of ruthenium(III) permits relatively low LMCT bands²⁹. The lowest absorption corresponding to spin-forbidden $^2T_{2g} \rightarrow ^2A_{2g}$ transition based on the low extinction coefficient value (ϵ) compared to charge transfer band at $\sim 38000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was found in 16260–19249 cm^{-1} and occurs in some cases as shoulders^{26,27} a

weak band at $\sim 25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ typical of $d-d$ transitions which is characteristic for the Ru^{III} ion persists^{30,31} in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Electronic absorption spectra of $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements for all the desired complexes of ruthenium(III) lies in the range of 1.79–1.93 B.M. which indicate the presence of one unpaired electron confirming a low spin t_{2g}^5 configuration and +3 oxidation state for ruthenium in all complexes^{29,32}.

Coordination of Schiff bases in the ruthenium(III) complexes is further confirmed by the ^1H NMR spectral data. Fig. 4 (A and B) shows the ^1H NMR spectra of ligand HL¹ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, in which a singlet is observed

Fig. 4. (A) ^1H NMR spectra HL¹ and (B) $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

at 2.31–2.48 ppm corresponding to the methyl ($-\text{CH}_3$) proton. A methoxy proton ($-\text{OCH}_3$) signal appeared as a sharp singlet in the region 3.80–3.98 ppm. The aromatic protons signal observed in the region of 6.42–8.35 ppm as multiplet, in the case of Ru^{III} complexes ^1H NMR

spectra, little bit broadening is observed in signals as compared to their respective ligands due to their paramagnetic nature³³⁻³⁵, Fig. 4(B). The azomethine proton (-HC=N-) was appeared singlet in the region of 8.36-9.44 ppm in ligands and in ruthenium(III) complexes it showed a downfield shift, indicating the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination^{33,34}. Singlet was observed for the hydroxyl (-OH) proton in the region of 9.84-9.93 ppm in free ligands, which was disappeared from this position in ruthenium(III) complexes which indicate the loss of hydroxy proton due to complexation³⁵. A singlet was observed at 11.01 and 10.49 ppm in [Ru(L¹)₂Cl.H₂O] and [Ru(L²)₂Cl.H₂O] may be corresponding to the coordinated water. The ¹H NMR spectral data is summarized in Table 3.

strong relationship with the binding mode in the water molecule of the respective metal chelates. Complexes (I) and (II) shows a loss of coordinated water^{34,36-39} at ~120-170 °C, above that temperature a subsequent loss of organic matter was observed. As a result of dehydration and decomposition, the observed weight losses for all complexes are in good agreement with the calculated values.

The antibacterial screening data are given in Table 4, which show that the compounds HL¹-HL³ and their ruthenium(III) complexes possess antibacterial activity. These results exhibited markedly an enhancement in activity on coordination with the metal ions. A possible mode for toxicity increases can be considered in terms of

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data of ligand and metal complexes

Comps.	¹ H NMR chemical shift (ppm)				
	CH ₃	OCH ₃	Aromatic	HC=N	OH
HL ¹	2.42	3.95	6.86-8.35	9.44	9.92
HL ²	2.39	3.94	6.85-7.26	8.63	9.93
HL ³	2.37	3.98	6.97-7.67	8.36	9.84
[Ru(L ¹) ₂ Cl.H ₂ O]	2.31	3.83	6.71-7.81	10.26	11.01 (~ Coordinated -OH ₂)
[Ru(L ²) ₂ Cl.H ₂ O]	2.48	3.83	6.42-7.33	8.93	10.49 (~ Coordinated -OH ₂)
[Ru(L ³) ₂ .Cl ₂]	2.32	3.80	6.71-7.42	8.94	-

The thermal behavior of the metal complexes was studied by recording thermogravimetric curves, Fig. 5. The temperature range for the dehydration process shows a

Fig. 5. Thermogravimetric curves of ruthenium(III) complexes.

Overtone's concept⁴⁰ and Tweedy's chelation theory⁴¹. According to Overtone's concept of the cell permeability, the lipid membrane that surrounds the cell favors the passage of only lipid-soluble materials. Therefore, liposolubility is an important factor which controls the antibacterial activity. On chelation, the polarity of metal ion will be reduced to the greater extent due to overlap with the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge between the metal ion and donor groups. Further it increases the delocalization of π electron over the whole chelate ring and thus enhances the lipophilicity of the complexes. This increased lipophilicity facilitates penetration of the complexes through lipid membranes and lead to blocking of the metal binding sites in the microbial enzymes. These complexes also disturb the cell respiration process and block the synthesis of proteins, thus suppressing the growth of the bacterial cell.

The morphology of compounds was studied using scan-

ning electron microscopy (SEM). Figs. 6–11 depicts the SEM picture of the compounds. The morphology of the compounds varied from wafer-like (HL^1), tiny rod like (HL^2), and nearly dumb-bell to spherical morphology

Fig. 6. SEM image of HL^1 .

Fig. 7. SEM image of $[Ru(L^1)_2Cl.H_2O]$.

Fig. 8. SEM image of HL^2 .

Fig. 9. SEM image of $[Ru(L^2)_2Cl.H_2O]$.

Fig. 10. SEM image of HL^3 .

Fig. 11. SEM image of $[Ru(L^3)_2Cl_2]$.

(HL^3) was evident from the SEM which further changed to spherical in shape for $[Ru(L^1)_2Cl.H_2O]$ consisting of a number of smaller particles (2–3 μm), brittle aggregates with no definite shape morphology for $[Ru(L^2)_2Cl.H_2O]$ and aggregation of small particles in to quasi-spherical

clusters of about 5–10 μm average size for $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^3)_2\cdot\text{Cl}_2]$ complex.

The analytical data indicate that metal : ligand stoichiometry in all complexes is 1 : 2. The propose study revealed an octahedral geometry of ruthenium(III) complexes, where as ligands acts as a bidentate chelating agents coordinating through the nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms. The results of antimicrobial activity data is as given in Table 4 shows that the ruthenium(III) complexes have more toxicity against the bacterial species than the parent ligands.

Table 4. Antibacterial screening data of ligands and metal complexes

Comps.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
HL ¹	9	16	7	10
HL ²		7	–	–
HL ³	7	7	15	7
$[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	12	12	9	–
$[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16	–	16	–
$[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^3)_2\cdot\text{Cl}_2]$	7	–	17	–
Solvent (DMSO)	–	–	–	–

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and were used without further purification. Distilled solvents were used throughout the experiments.

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

The Schiff bases were prepared by the general procedure²³. The Schiff base HL¹ was prepared by condensing equimolar quantities of 25 mL hot ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde 1×10^{-3} mol (0.152 g) and 25 mL hot ethanolic solution of 2-amino-4-methylpyridine 1×10^{-3} mol (0.108 g) in 25 mL hot ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5–6 h on water bath. The solution was reduced to ¼th of its original volume and poured over crushed ice. The orange precipitate was filtered, washed several times with cold methanol and recrystallized from ethanol. The purity of ligands was checked by thin layer chromatography and elemental analysis. Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of HL², 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 4-methylaniline and HL³, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 4-methylaniline.

Synthesis of $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^1)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (I) :

A 20 mL portion of a 2×10^{-3} mol (0.484 g) solution of HL¹ in ethanol was added dropwise over a period of 10 min to 20 mL of a 1×10^{-3} mol (0.261 g) $\text{RuCl}_3\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution in ethanol under continuous stirring and heating (80 °C). The reaction mixture was heated in a round bottom flask equipped with a water condenser for 2 h. After 50–55 min, the solution turned turbid and a dark green precipitate separated which was allowed to crystallize for 3 h. Then, the precipitate was collect by vacuum evaporation of solvent, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 .

Synthesis of $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^2)_2\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (II) :

A 20 mL portion of a 2×10^{-3} mol (0.482 g) solution of HL² in ethanol was added dropwise over a period of 10 min to 20 mL of a 1×10^{-3} mol (0.261 g) $\text{RuCl}_3\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution in ethanol under continuous stirring and heating (60 °C). The reaction mixture was heated in a round bottom flask equipped with a water condenser for 4 h. After 2 h, the solution turned dark reddish-black in color, (pH was adjusted to optimum level) refluxed the reaction mixture on water bath for 5–6 h then the volume of the reaction mixture was reduced to ¼th of its original volume and poured over crushed ice to yield black colour precipitate. The precipitate was allowed to stand for 24 h, then filtered off, washed with hot water, ethanol and dried in oven at 105 °C.

Similar procedure were adopted for the synthesis of $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^3)_2\cdot\text{Cl}_2]$ (III).

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis was carried out on Euro Vector, CHNS-O Analyzer, EA 3000, Italy. The metal content of all the metal complexes were determined on ICP-AES Jobinyvon Horiba ultima 2. The molar conductivity of ligands and complexes were recorded using 1×10^{-3} M solution in DMSO on Equip-Tronics conductivity meter EQ-660A. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded at room temperature as KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One FTIR spectrometer in the range from 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The electronic absorption spectra were recorded on a UV-2401 PC Shimadzu spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature on a Gouy's balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ g cm^{-3}) as a standard. Diamagnetic

corrections were made using Pascal's constants³². ¹H NMR spectra were obtained from Bruker Advance 2, 300 MHz NMR spectrometer. TGA measurements were obtained from Pyris Diamond TG/DT analyzer supplied by Perkin-Elmer.

In vitro antibacterial screening was performed by the agar disc diffusion method⁴². The sterile discs impregnated with test compounds (1 mg/mL in DMSO) were placed on the seeded plates. The zone of inhibition around the disc indicated the antibacterial activity of the test compounds. The tests were carried out in duplicate for each of compound. The morphologies of the compounds were analyzed using an FEI Quanta-200 Scanning Electron Microscope with an operating voltage of 10 kV.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Mumbai, for facilities and Icon Analytical Equipment Pvt. Ltd. for SEM analysis. One of the authors (SD) is thankful to the UGC (Green Chemistry and Green Technology), New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

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